

Comparison of P_s and E_m values reveals that the permselectivity is well reflected in the membrane potential. The membrane selectivity decreases with increase in the concentration of co-ions. Within the pores there will be a diffused ionic atmosphere from the charged wall and thickness of this atmosphere would depend upon the electrolyte concentration. In a very dilute solution in contact with the membrane, the thickness of the atmosphere becomes so great that only cations would be present in the pores and the membrane is only cation permeable (high value of P_s). As the concentration increases, the thickness of the ionic atmosphere decreases and the anions would also be able to enter the pores. It is clear that with very high concentrations the membrane would lose its permselectivity for cations.

(iii) *Mobility of anions(v)*: The apparent mobilities of anions for the membranes under study for lithium, sodium, potassium, magnesium, calcium and barium have been determined. The mobility of anions can be calculated with the help of membrane potential⁷.

The mobility value of anion is influenced by factors such as, (i) the valency of the anions; (ii) the various factors *viz.* the charge on the membrane, porosity of the membrane, the charge and size of the diffusing ion, adsorption and exchange capacity of membrane material which are operative in the movement of anions in the pores; (iii) the chances of entry of anions in the pores and (iv) the mobility of the anions in the free solution.

The clogging of the pores by the adsorbed ions would greatly influence factors (i) and (ii). If the pores are clogged to a large extent, the electrical forces would be playing an important role. Similarly, size of the anions would influence the entry inside the pores. In the free solution and at infinite dilution, the mobilities follow the order⁸ of $SO_4^{2-} > Cl^- > NO_3^-$. But the mobilities calculated from the potential data for anions (having common cation, K^+) at 0.01/0.001M concentration are $Cl^- > NO_3^- > SO_4^{2-}$. The calculated values are quite different from the order of the mobility in the free solutions.

It is observed that the mobilities of the ions increase with increase in concentration of the solution. The results can be explained on the basis of Willis theory⁷. According to this, there would be a diffused ionic atmosphere within pores of the membrane extending from the negatively charged walls, whose thickness would depend upon the concentration of the electrolyte in contact with the membrane. At a certain concentration, an equilibrium would be set up between the fixed ions in the pores and those in the solution in its immediate vicinity. The thickness of the ionic atmosphere would be maximum when the electrolyte solution is very dilute. An increase in ionic atmosphere would lead to greater repulsion, thus, resulting in the lowest value for mobility of anions. On the other hand, with the increase in concentration, the ionic atmosphere decreases resulting in an increase in the mobility values. At still higher concentrations

maximum reduction of ionic atmosphere takes place and from that point onward the membrane effect would almost vanish and the ionic mobility value would approximately be the same as observed in the case of free diffusion.

(iv) *Membrane selectivity*: Membrane potentials have been regarded for a long time a measure of the membrane selectivity. The measurement of ion activity by means of membrane electrodes is most successful in the concentration range over which the membrane behaves as an ideally selective one i.e., $P_s = 1$ and obeys the Nernst's equation. The membrane under investigation is found to be ideally selective for only two electrolytes, *viz.* Na_2SO_4 and K_2SO_4 over a concentration range 0.02 to 0.1M.

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Synthesis of 3-Benzoylhydrazone-2-Indolinones, 1-Methyl-3-Benzoylhydrazone-2-Indolinones and 1-Morpholino/Piperidinomethyl-3-Benzoylhydrazone-2-Indolinones†

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A number of 3-arylimino-2-indolinones and their 1-methyl and 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl analogs were synthesised recently as excystment and cysticidal agents¹⁻³. The present communication describes the synthesis of several 3-benzoylhydrazone-2-indolinones(I), 1-methyl-3-benzoylhydrazone-2-indolinones(II) and 1-morpholino/piperidinomethyl-3-benzoylhydrazone-2-indolinones(III).

† Part XVIII of the series of Potential Biologically Active Agents.